

Pine Needles as Bio-Fuel

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ABSTRACT

Day by day human needs are increasing and the fact is that we have certain limit of fossil fuels on earth. Bio fuels can be used as the substitute of fossil fuels. The beautiful example of biofuel is making of coal from *Pine Needles*. *Uttarakhand* has developed a new bio-fuel that is used in place of coal, a highly polluting fossil fuel, and provides additional income to locals. The source of the bio-fuel is pine needles, which fall on ground during summer and cause forest fires because of the high concentration of resin in them. In a bid to prevent the fires, the forest department initiated a pilot project in *Chamoli* district where local companies bought pine needles collected by village women at Re 1 per kg. **"On an average, a village woman earned Rs. 70 a day this year,"**-Anil Baluni(vice-chairperson of the state's environment advisory team) who supervised the project in *Chamoli*. Initially, pine needles were used as fuel directly, but it did not work due to the presence of different nitrogen oxides. Now the pine needles are burnt in a closed kiln so that nitrogen compounds could evaporate through hydrolysis. Fifty tonnes of pine needle bricks can replace 30 tonnes of coal at half the price of coal. This saves 71 tonnes of carbon emission, the department officials said. The half-burnt material is mixed with the by-products obtained from biogas plant which uses cow dung as a major constituent. In this way an innovative concept has been introduced in the field of bio fuels which is not only using a different source but will also prevent wastage by reusing by-products for a better purpose.